

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

INTERMEDIARY REPORT

on synergies and collaboration
Deliverable 5.4

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Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the collaborative activities, synergies and meaningful interactions with relevant initiatives and projects the AGEMERA project has achieved in its first half (M1-M18). It provides details on the activities regarding collaboration and synergies with sister projects, related initiatives and the members of the mineral exploration and raw materials community. These activities have aimed to exploit potential synergies with other Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects and related initiatives, as well as support cross-fertilisation. For example, a notable event in which AGEMERA took part was the EU SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference, which brought together 124 industry experts, researchers, and professionals in the raw materials sector from all around the world in Rovaniemi, Finland, on 30-31 October 2023.

Specific activities on establishing collaboration and synergies are intended to facilitate knowledge exchange within the mining and mineral exploration community, help increase impact in the EU and beyond through communicating and disseminating the results, and support closer collaboration in the future. This document provides an interim summary of these activities carried out by multiple partners in AGEMERA, supported and coordinated by GEO and the University of Oulu (Project Coordinator).

1. Project background

As the global demand for CRMs continues to grow rapidly, mobilising Europe's domestic potential is an essential part of the EU's move towards becoming more resilient and developing an open strategic autonomy. Europe has a long tradition of mining and extractive activities in base metals such as copper and zinc, yet it has been less successful in developing projects to source CRMs, even though there is significant potential for these. The main bottlenecks are the lack of investment in exploration and mining, the diverse and lengthy national permitting procedures, and the low levels of public acceptance.

The EU's transition to a low-carbon, digital economy requires innovative tools, technologies, and techniques to be used in mineral exploration. AGEMERA conducts extensive geological and geophysical surveys, across an area of approximately 4700 km² and demonstrating three novel, non-invasive methods, to map resources in six EU countries and one third country (Zambia). The project uses various types of data to improve the genetic mineral system models of deposit types known to contain CRM. At the same time, an open-access SoftGIS database is being developed to gain a better understanding of people's social, cultural, environmental, and economic concerns related to mining and mineral exploration. AGEMERA also raises awareness on the importance of CRM for the green and digital transition by producing an educational package for schools and universities together with an online serious game and by organising public events to reach wider audiences.

On this journey, the collaboration activities and synergies with other initiatives and projects help convey the message of AGEMERA more effectively, and increase impact.

2. Main areas of collaboration and synergies

To exploit potential collaboration and synergies with initiatives and projects relevant to AGEMERA, various avenues are being explored by the consortium within the framework of the project activities. These include:

- Clustering events serving as a platform for structured exchange of information, mutual learning, greater visibility and cross-fertilisation;
- Conference participation and networking to establish direct contacts with relevant projects and initiatives and contribute with input based on AGEMERA's activities and results;
- Participation in meetings and events of other projects to introduce AGEMERA and its activities and hear about the other projects' activities with a view to identifying potential synergies and avoiding overlaps in similar activities.

The following sections provide details on AGEMERA's involvement in the clustering activities as well as in the events in the field of raw materials during the first 18 months of the project.

3. Clustering with sister projects

3.1 EU Supercluster Lapland Geoconference

AGEMERA was part of the EU SuperCluster Lapland Geoconference, which took place in Rovaniemi, Finland, on 30-31 October 2023. The event was organised by the [EIS \(Exploration Information System\) project](#) coordinated by GTK-Geological Survey of Finland, and it brought together 124 industry experts, researchers, and professionals in the raw materials sector from all around the world. The event's focus was on the current technological challenges and topics in the field, and it provided a great opportunity to build valuable connections with sister projects and related initiatives and professionals.

AGEMERA's contributions to the event were multiple. The project coordinator, Jari Joutsenvaara, moderated the first session on the topic of innovative mineral exploration. The project was also introduced in this session by Marko Holma from Muon Solutions, one of the AGEMERA partners, who presented its mission and objectives with a focus on the innovative technologies developed and deployed in the project, including the muon-based density surveys his company is conducting. On the second day, Leena Suopajärvi from the University of Lapland, one of AGEMERA's academic partners, presented the preliminary results of their work concerning the local perception on mineral exploration and mining, based on the first questionnaires, which were conducted that resulted in 300 respondents providing their opinions and concerns. Lastly, AGEMERA was featured in the poster exhibition of the event alongside various sister projects. The poster's design was created by GEO based on the content provided by the coordinator, and it was the starting point of discussions concerning potential collaborations with other participants. Participants were also given AGEMERA flyers that included the key information about the project and its partners, as well as a QR code leading to the website and the social media handles to boost the visibility of its online communication activities. A selection of photos from the event can be seen below.

Pic. 2-3-4-5: AGEMERA participating in the SuperCluster event 2023

3.2 EIS project kick-off meeting

AGEMERA was presented and introduced at the kick-off meeting of the EIS project, one of AGEMERA's sister projects.

3.3 AGEMERA project kick-off meeting

Sister projects EIS, VECTOR, SEMACRET and GoldenEye were allocated specific timeslots in the agenda of AGEMERA's kick-off and presented their objectives and planned activities,

3.4 Dissemination Workshop: SEMACRET, EIS and GOLDENEYE

AGEMERA had a clustering event with our sister projects SEMACRET, EIS and GOLDENEYE. A dissemination and clustering expert, Juha Kaija, gave a detailed workshop on how to deal with data requests and social media targeting of raw material-related projects. There were several suggestions and practical advice discussed at the workshop to communicate results effectively and in a joint fashion.

3.5 MULTIMINER project kick-off and further collaboration

MultiMiner, a Horizon Europe project working on remote sensing, invited AGEMERA to its kick-off event. The project is coordinated by the Geological Survey of Finland, with which future cooperation possibilities were discussed. It was an initial step in cooperating with sister projects.

AGEMERA is currently in discussions with the MultiMiner project, which aims to form of a network of mining projects in Europe. Their first envisioned activity would be the organisation and delivery of a joint quarterly or biannual newsletter to inform the general public, but also the industry, on the progress the projects are making and any recent developments. AGEMERA intends to contribute to this joint newsletter by sharing news concerning its progress and any new results that may come up in the upcoming months.

4. Raw Material Related Events

4.1 Clusters meet regions 2023, Finland

A Clusters meet Regions, and Matchmaking event was organised in Finland with the primary aim of facilitating matchmaking and strengthening the capacity of regional clusters in the field of sustainable mineral exploration. It was by the European Cluster Collaboration Platform, on behalf of the European Commission and in partnership with the East & North Finland EU office and MINE.THE.GAP H2020 InnoSup.

There were around 150 representatives in person from European clusters, local, regional, national, and European public authorities, as well as industry and civil society stakeholders, who shared their experience and provided insights into the role of clusters in increasing the responsible utilisation of raw materials. AGEMERA project coordinator Jari Joutsenvaara and partner Muon Solutions promoted the AGEMERA project at several face-to-face discussions. For example, a networking meeting was held with a Bulgarian business development delegate.

4.2 EU Mining Regional Innovation Ecosystems by OECD

Within the context of the Raw Materials Week in 2023, a session was organised by the OECD and S3P Mining Industry as part of the MINE.THE.GAP project, with the aim of exploring cooperation possibilities within regions to support the supply of raw materials in the EU and discussing investment and policy alignment potentials.

The meeting brought together the OECD mining regions and cities initiative and the S3P Mining Industry thematic partnership. AGEMERA project, with Polish partners, was spotlighted to Polish mining officials.

4.3 ERA-MIN3

Within the context of the Raw Materials Week in 2023, a new development workshop was held jointly with ERA-MIN3. Ongoing EU projects, such as AGEMERA, and future possibilities were discussed with various participants. During the workshop, there was room to discuss ideas for further actions and implementations of the Partnership.

4.4 EIT Raw Materials Week 2022-2023

The events offered great possibilities for clustering with various stage Horizon Europe projects and project initiatives. AGEMERA took part in the EU Horizon Success stories

event with projects like ROBOMINERS, SUSMAGPRO, FineFuture and GoldenEye. The last one being a project in which the University of Oulu is also taking part in.

As one major part of the AGEMERA project is to promote the UNFC and UNRMS, Raw Materials Week provided excellent insights and practical examples of how the Framework Classification and Management systems have been implemented in Europe and why they provide a globally harmonised tool for estimating and monitoring the social, economic and environmental feasibility.

Pic. 1: AGEMERA coordinator Jari Joutsenvaara (on the right) standing with Sanna Uusitalo (middle) and Andreas Knoblock (left) from the GoldenEye project at the EIT Raw Materials Week 2022

5. Conclusions

Specific activities on establishing collaboration and creating synergies with relevant projects and initiatives were planned and are being implemented in AGEMERA. In its first 18 months, partners in AGEMERA have already conducted a significant number of such activities involving AGEMERA's sister projects, related initiatives, and the members of the mineral exploration and raw materials community. These activities have aimed to exploit potential synergies, support cross-fertilisation and avoid overlaps in certain project activities.

Specific opportunities to maintain and further enhance collaboration and synergies have already been identified for the upcoming period of the project. GEO, in conjunction with OU, will continue monitoring these and will encourage all the partners to take advantage of these opportunities.

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